

**ASSESSMENT OF THE AVAILABILITY OF SAFETY AND SECURITY
FACILITIES IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN KADUNA:
IMPLICATION FOR UNIVERSAL BASIC
EDUCATION CURRICULUM**

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Abstract:

The study investigated the availability of safety and security facilities in public primary schools in Kaduna state. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A questionnaire titled "Availability of Safety and Security Facilities in Public Primary Schools" (ASSFPPS) was used for data collection. Twenty (20) randomly selected primary schools were used for the study. A total of Fifty (50) head teachers and teachers participated by responding to the items on the questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using frequencies and percentages. The findings of the study revealed the dearth of safety and security facilities in primary schools in Kaduna, as there were only very few of such facilities available in the schools that were visited. It was recommended as a matter of urgency that government should provide safety and security facilities such as fences with security barbwire, lockable gates, metal detectors, fire extinguishers, uniformed armed security personnel, close circuit television cameras, among others. Head teachers and other school personnel should be security conscious and alert at all times. School authorities should beef up security in all nooks and corners of their schools to make their schools safe havens for teaching and learning. All staff should be trained in safety and security management. Safety and security concepts should be included in the universal basic education curriculum across all classes to create the necessary awareness in the most vulnerable children in our society. A school environment devoid of crime, abduction, rape, violence and the likes is a place where

meaningful learning can take place. Safety and security should be regarded as the business of all and the responsibility of all. Therefore, all hands must be on deck to make our society safe and sound in order to achieve global security.

Keywords: safety and security, safety facilities, primary schools

Introduction

In schools across the country and the world in general, students routinely encounter a range of safety and security issues from overt acts of violence and bullying to subtle overt intimidation and disrespect. Though extreme incidents such as school shootings tend to attract global attention, day to day incidents such as fights, yelling, quarrels between teachers and students contribute to students over all sense of safety and shape the learning climate in the schools. In many public schools in Nigeria, teachers and students have reported feeling unsafe in the school compound, classrooms and the area just outside the school buildings due to possible incessant terrorist attacks (Ugwumba and Odom, 2015; Yusuf, 2012, 2013).

The current terrorist group called Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria is threatening to halt or even reverse educational progress. Education is constantly under attack in northern Nigeria. Since the beginning of 2012, according to Amnesty International's Research (2013), about 70 teachers and over 1000 school children have been killed or wounded. About 50 schools have either been burned or seriously damaged and more than 60 others have been forced to close. Thousands of children have been forced out of schools across communities in Yobe, Kaduna, Adamawa, Borno States. Many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety to other states. The higher number of attacks was in Borno state in the North-east. According to the Nigeria teacher's union, more than 1000 teachers have been forced to flee from areas in the north since 2012. Based on this backdrop of adverse effect of Boko Haram on education in Nigeria, one is inclined to ask the question; how safe are schools in Nigeria, at the peak of Boko Haram insurgency? While parents, teachers, students and other stakeholders in education continue to cry out through various media channels for the root causes of school violence to be addressed, they are simultaneously pressing for practical measures to make public schools a safe environment for teaching and learning. The expectation of every parent who sends his/her child/ward to school is that the child/ward should be properly taught and should return home safe and sound. Since the primary purpose of schools is to teach, why not make the schools safe, free from crime and any form of violence?

It is in the light of the safety and security concerns expressed by students, parents and stakeholders that this research is undertaken to assess the safety and security facilities available in public primary schools in Kaduna metropolis.

Review of related literature

The security of innocent children in educational institutions in Nigeria by threat of Boko Haram attack should be seen in the context of the wider problem of the impact of conflict and violence. The immediate impact of attacks include the loss of, injury to, or abduction of students, teachers and personnel and damage of buildings and facilities most typically due to the burning, bombing or shelling of buildings or transport facilities by Boko Haram. For instance, the officials of education system closed 85 schools in north-eastern Borno, affecting nearly 120,000 students, after a spate of attacks by Islamic militants, in an area that has the country's worst literacy rate (The Guardian, 2014). More than 200 school girls kidnapped on the night of 14th April, 2014, remain missing at the time of this work and currently have been forced into marriage with members of Boko Haram with a reputed "bride price" of ₦2,000 each (Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia).

These attacks have forced the affected state government to close down schools and colleges for prolonged periods. This is an area that is reckoned to be educationally poor-performing even by Nigeria standards. Low school enrolment-especially of girls, low retention rates, high number of out of school children and grinding poverty already characterize northern Nigeria (The Guardian, 2014). The school closure could have far reaching consequences, including ending the education of some students in a region where few ever have the opportunity to get to further their education (Bako, 2014; Aminu, 2013).

Generally, it has been recorded that between 2012 till date, the insecurity generated by the constant attacks and fighting in Borno and other states in the North-Eastern part of Nigeria has led many parents to send their children away or leave the state, disrupting their education (Amnesty International, 2013). According to documents provided by Director of Basic and Secondary Education in the Federal Ministry of Education, in 2013, schools in the north-east recorded the lowest number in recent years of pupil who applied and were admitted into junior secondary schools in the country. In one school in Mungono, out of 160 eligible pupils, only 60 applied for admission into junior secondary school in 2013. An official in the Ministry of Education in Borno state reportedly stated that "around 15,000 children in Borno state have stopped attending classes". The list of various attacks by Boko Haram on educational

institutions since 2012 is endless. The attacks have been presented and summarized in a tabular form. They have unleashed fear and terror in the minds of the teachers, students, education administrators, government, parents and citizens staying in these parts of the country thereby affecting education and the educational system in Nigeria.

Table A: Boko Haram attacks on Nigerian Schools (Education)

Date	Venue	Casualty	Nature of attack
Feb 17, 2012	Borno state	No death	Boko Haram destroyed gomari costain primary school by fire.
Feb 22, 2012	Borno state	No death	Abba Ganaram primary school Maiduguri was set ablaze by Boko Haram.
April 11, 2012	Damaturu	-	Boko Haram attacked and bombed police station and one primary school.
May 12, 2012	Maiduguri	-	Boko Haram burnt a private nursery, primary and secondary school in Maiduguri.
May 13, 2012	Maiduguri	-	Boko Haram burnt Mafa central school in Maiduguri.
Aug 19, 2012	Yobe	-	Boko Haram attacked and blew up a primary school, church and police station in Maiduguri.
March 18, 2013	Borno state	3 dead, 7 injured	Boko Haram on 4 public schools in Maiduguri killing 3 teachers injured 4 people and 3 students.
April 7, 2013	Borno state	1 dead	Gunmen attacked and killed a teacher in Gwange III primary school in Maiduguri.
Junu 18, 2013	Damaturu	11 dead	Boko Haram attack on GSS Damaturu, shooting sporadically, killing 7 students, 2 teachers and 2 gunmen, Headed to the teachers, 6 students sustained various degrees of injuries.
July 6, 2013	Yobe state	42 dead	Boko Haram attacked GSS mamudo in Yobe state. Killing 41 students and a teacher.
Sept 29, 2013	Yobe state	41 dead	Boko Haram stormed a dormitory of college of agriculture in Gujiba Yobe state killing 40 students and a teacher.
Feb 25, 2014	Yobe state	29 dead	Boko Haram stormed a co-educational, federal government college boarding school in Buni Yadi killing 29 male students, injured 59, abducted some female students, some girls ordered to quit school and get married or be killed in future attacks.
April 14, 2014	Borno state	16 dead	Boko Haram attacked Girls secondary school and kidnapped 234 Chibok girls, burnt library and other government properties.

Source: Wikipedia, the Free encyclopedia (May 13, 2014), Thisday live (2014).

Similarly, in other parts of the world such as United States of America (USA), statistics published in 2013 by the U.S Department of Education and the U.S Department of Justice Paint a sobering picture of life at school for more than 50 million public school students in America.

According to the report, there were 31 school-associated violent deaths of students, staff, and other people from July 1, 2010, through June 30, 2011. Of these deaths, 25 were homicides and 6 were suicides; 11 of the homicides and 3 of the suicides were youth ages 5 to 18. Furthermore, in 2011, students ages 12 to 18 were victims of about 1.25 million non-fatal crimes at school, including about 649,000 thefts and 598,000 violent crimes such as assault (www.vlt.fi/inf/pdf/researchhighlights/2013/rio.pdf).

Given these school safety statistics, as well as the series of high-profile school shootings from Columbine High School in Colorado in 1999 to Sandy Hook Elementary in Connecticut in 2012, it's hardly surprising that school safety and security have become top-of-the-agenda items for many public school districts across the United States. Mayer and Leone (1991) describe a study of student feelings of safety at school, both before and after the Columbine shooting, which revealed that the violence in Colorado had an impact on perceptions of school safety across the nation. While the majority of students did not report experiencing fear at school before or after Columbine, students were more likely to report being afraid of harm or attack at school after the shooting than before (Mayer and Leone, 1991).

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the safety and security facilities available in public primary schools in Kaduna.
2. To ascertain the adequacy of the safety and security facilities in public schools in Kaduna.

Research Questions

1. *What are the safety and security facilities available in public primary schools in Kaduna?*
2. *How adequate are the safety and security facilities available in public primary schools in Kaduna?*

Methodology

The research design for the study is descriptive survey design. The population for the study consists of all the forty two public primary schools in Kaduna North Local government Education Authority (LGEA). Twenty five randomly selected primary schools from Kaduna metropolis were used for the study. A total of fifty (50) teachers were used for the study (i.e. 25 head teachers and teachers). A structured Questionnaire

tagged “Availability of safety and security facilities in Public Primary Schools (ASSFPPS) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was made up of two sections. Section one addressed the issue of availability of safety and security facilities in public schools in Kaduna. The second section addressed the issue of adequacy of the safety and security facilities in public primary schools in Kaduna. The instrument was validated through a pilot test that was carried out in LEA Primary School, Tudun Wada, Kaduna State. The instrument was piloted-test using seventeen (17) teachers who were not part of the main study but had the same qualifications as those used in the main study. A test re-test approach using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to establish the reliability. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.79. Data collected from the study were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics, frequency counts and simple percentages.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Research Question 1

What are the safety and security facilities available in public primary schools in Kaduna?

Table 1 was used to answer research question 1.

Table 1: Mean and standard Deviation scores of views of Head teachers and teachers on safety and security facilities available in public primary schools in Kaduna metropolis

S/N	Safety & Facilities	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.	Fence	1.33	0.438
2.	Lockable main gate	1.84	0.430
3.	Metal detector	1.20	0.341
4.	Close circuit TV cameras	1.20	0.341
5.	Central security alarm	1.20	0.341
6.	Well-equipped first Aid box	1.20	0.341
7.	Uniform security personnel	1.33	0.438
8.	Clearly marked designated entrances with security metal detector doors	1.15	0.230
9.	Fire extinguishers	1.85	0.847
10.	Fire alarm	1.85	0.849
11.	Lighting in and around school compound	1.89	0.431
12.	Main office centrally located	1.20	0.341
13.	Classrooms with lockable windows and doors	1.15	0.230
14.	Security barbwire on fence	1.18	0.234
15.	Well fenced play ground	1.21	0.345
16.	Intercom systems	1.20	0.341

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17.	Radio communication	1.22	0.347
18.	Walky talky Walkman	1.21	0.345
19.	Cell phone	1.85	0.849
20.	Security club	1.15	0.230
21.	Safety and training programme	1.15	0.230

Table 1 shows that all the twenty one items had mean scores below the cut-off of 2.5 on a four point Likert scale. This indicates that there is a dearth of safety and security facilities in public primary schools in Kaduna metropolis.

Table 2: Head Teachers and Teachers responses to Questionnaire on Availability of Safety and Security Facilities/Equipment in Public Primary Schools in Kaduna

S/No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	My school has a fence	40	8	1	1
2.	My school has a lockable main gate	38	10	2	0
3.	Security personnel have metal detectors	50	0	0	0
4.	There are close circuit TV cameras in my school	50	0	0	0
5.	There are central security alarm	50	0	0	0
6.	There is a well-equipped first aid box	35	10	2	3
7.	There are uniformed security personnel	40	6	2	2
8.	There are clearly marked designated entrance with security metal detector doors	45	4	1	0
9.	There fire extinguishers in strategic locations	42	5	2	1
10.	We have fire alarm	45	3	1	2
11.	We have adequate lighting in and around the school compound	36	7	5	2
12.	Our administrative office is centrally located	25	10	10	5
13.	All our classrooms have lockable doors and windows	30	10	5	5
14.	We have security barbwire on our fence	50	0	0	0
15.	Our playground is well fenced	36	7	5	2
16.	We have interim systems	50	0	0	0
17.	We have adequate radio communication	50	0	0	0
18.	Our security guards have walky talky	50	0	0	0
19.	I have a personal cell phone	41	5	2	2
20.	My school has an official cell phone	50	0	0	0
21.	My school has a security club	50	0	0	0
22.	My school has a regular safety & security training for staffs	50	0	0	0

Table 2 shows that almost all the head teachers and teachers strongly disagreed on the availability and adequacy of safety and security facilities/equipment available in public primary schools in Kaduna metropolis. This indicates that majority of schools (95%) do not have basic safety and security facilities/equipment such as school fence, lockable gate, uniformed security personnel, fire extinguishers, first aid box, fire alarm, classrooms with lockable doors and windows. Most of the doors and windows available in some of the schools visited have broken classes and are in very bad shape. All the twenty (20) schools visited had no metal detectors, close circuit cameras, metal detector entrance doors, barbwire fence, intercoms, walky talky, and radio communications. Security clubs have not been established in all the twenty schools visited.

Table 3: Safety and Security facilities

SAFETY & SECURITY FACILITIES	SCHOOLS																				REMARKS
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	
Fence	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	NA	NA	AV	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	AV	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Availability only in 4 out of the 20 schools visited
Lockable main gate	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	AV	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Available only in 2 out of the 20 schools visited
Metal detectors	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Close circuit TV cameras	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Central security alarm	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Well-equipped first Aid Box	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Uniformed security personnel	NA	AV	AV	NA	Available in only in 2 out of the 20 schools visited																
Clearly marked designated entrance with metal detector doors	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Fire extinguishers	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	Available only in two out of the 20 schools visited						
Fire alarm	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Lighting in & around school compound	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	NA	NA	AV	NA	Available only in 3 out of the 20 schools visited						
Centrally located main office	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	NA	NA	AV	NA	Available only in 4 out of the 20 schools visited						
Classrooms with lockable windows and doors	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	NA	Available only in 5 out of the 20 schools visited. Most windows and doors are either broken or in bad shape.														
Security barbwire	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Well fenced playground	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	AV	AV	NA	Available only in 2 out of the 20 schools visited										
Intercom system	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Radio communication	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Walky talky two way communication	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Personal cell phones	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	AV	Available in all 20 schools visited
Official cell phones	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Security club	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited
Safety & Security training programme for staff	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not available in all 20 schools visited

Table 3 indicates that most schools (95%) do not have basic safety and security facilities/equipment. For instance, only 3 (15%) schools out of 20 had a basic facility such as schools fence surrounding their compound and play ground. seventeen (17) i.e. 85% had no fence. This could make the schools very accessible to intruders. Only two schools out of the twenty (20) schools had lockable main entrance with uniform security personnel's. Eighteen (18) out of the twenty (20) schools had no gates and no uniformed security personnel's.

Table 4: Adequacy of the safety, security, and facilities/equipment available Safety facilities

S/No	Safety and Security facilities	Frequency	Adequate %	Not adequate %	Total
1.	Fence	3	15	85	100
2	Lockable main gate	2	10	90	100
3.	Metal detector	0	0	100	100
4.	Close circuit TV cameras	0	0	100	100
5.	Central security alarm	0	0	100	100
6.	Well-equipped first Aid box	0	0	100	100
7.	Uniform security personnel	2	10	90	100
8.	Clearly marked designated entranced with security metal detector doors	0	0	100	100
9.	Fire extinguishers	2	10	90	100
10.	Fire alarm	0	0	100	100
11.	Lighting in and around school compound	3	15	85	100
12.	Main office centrally located	4	20	80	100
13.	Classrooms with lockable windows and doors	5	25	75	100
14.	Security barbwire on fence	0	0	100	100
15.	Well fenced play ground	2	10	90	100
16.	Intercom systems	0	0	100	100
17.	Radio communication	0	0	100	100
18.	Walky talky Walkman	0	0	100	100
19.	Cell phone	20	100	-	100
20.	Security club	0	0	100	100
21.	Safety and training programme	0	0	100	100
22.		0	0	100	100

Table 4 shows that all the twenty one safety and security facilities/equipment listed were either not available or available but grossly inadequate. All schools visited had no security clubs for pupils and staffs are not trained on safety and security management.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have led to the conclusion that there is dearth of safety and security facilities/equipment in public primary schools in Kaduna, as there were only very few of such facilities/equipment available in the schools that were visited. Majority of the schools visited were not fenced, no main entrance gates, no armed security personnel's, thus making the schools very porous and vulnerable to insurgent attacks. Most of the classrooms are in very bad shape with broken windows and doors. The presence of hawkers loitering around further poses additional security threats. Government and school authorities should, as a matter of urgency, provide all the necessary safety and security facilities/equipment in schools to make them safe for pupils, teachers and other school personnel's. A school environment devoid of crime, abduction, rape, violence and the likes is a place where meaningful, productive and impactful learning can take place.

Implication for Universal Basic Education Curriculum

- The Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) in collaboration with state Universal Basic Education Boards (SUBEBS) should invite curriculum experts to a curriculum writing workshop on "safety and security in schools".
- Curriculum planners and developers should ensure that the proposed Universal Basic Education Curriculum on Safety and Security is aimed at exposing children to fight for their rights against the following; child abuse, child molestation, child sexual harassment, child trafficking and other forms of violence.
- In view of the fact that pupils at the Universal Basic Education levels (i.e. foundation level) are the most vulnerable in the society, there is the need for them to undergo vigorous training on how to be safe in school and in an insecure world.
- The proposed new Universal Basic Education curriculum on safety and security should include among others, the following topics; security awareness, security conscious, security alert, security tools, crime, violence, terrorism, trauma, bullying, law enforcement agencies/agents and so on.

Recommendations

1. Government and all school authorities concerned should as a matter of urgency provide all the necessary safety and security facilities/equipment such as fences

with security barbwire, gates, metal detectors, windows and lockable windows and doors, fire extinguishers, fire alarm, central alarm, CCTV Cameras and the like equipment in all primary schools in Kaduna state.

2. School authorities of all public primary schools in Kaduna should beef up security in their schools by hiring uniform trained security personnel's to the main entrance to all primary schools. They should also trim all trees and shrubs and providing adequate lighting in all hooks and corners of their schools.
3. Head teachers and other school personnel's should be security conscious and alert at all times.
4. School authorities should strive to make their schools safe havens for teaching and learning by providing safety and security training programmes for pupils, teachers, and other school personnel's.
5. Safety and security concepts should be included in the universal basic education curriculum across all classes to create the necessary awareness in the most vulnerable children in the society.
6. Security clubs should be established in all public primary schools to educate them on safety and security.
7. Pupils, teachers, other school personnel's should be provided with ID card that must be worn at all times. This will keep outsiders and unauthorized persons from sneaking into the school.
8. Head teachers and teachers must conduct routine security inspections of the interior and exterior of their schools and report any suspicious activity to the appropriate quarters.
9. School authorities must prohibit hawking and loitering of unauthorized persons within and outside the school premises and its surroundings.

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